

Sacralization of the Fifth Lumbar Vertebra: Under-Reported and Misunderstood

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ABSTRACT

Archaeological finds are made in the field, and the museum. Modern human osteological analyses utilize documented collections and clinical studies to test observations. However, if researchers inadvertently conflate criteria, findings cannot be truly comparable.

The most common form of lumbosacral transitional vertebrae is sacralization, with eight variants, only considered ‘complete’ when one or both sides have bony fusion. Complete sacralization reportedly occurs in 1.5%-14% of archaeological and modern populations; yet differentiation of variants is underreported in the literature. Studies can conflate most or all types, resulting in rates as high as 46%.

Sacralization is compared between *Mary Rose* and *Kronan*. Both samples have 16.7% true prevalence of complete sacralization; 38.3% of *Mary Rose* sacra and 26.7% of *Kronan* sacra show some variant of sacralization. Results suggest complete sacralization among medieval and early modern populations is higher than previously recognized; further, observations of sacralization must be consistently delineated by type.

Diagnostic criteria; Standardized observation; Lumbosacral transitional vertebrae (LSTV); Sacralization; Kronan; Mary Rose

INTRODUCTION

Archaeological finds are made in the field, whether above water or below; and in museum storerooms. Most osteological analyses of human remains have, in recent years, utilized documented collections and clinical studies to test the veracity of observations and subsequent claims (Matos and Santos 2006; Brickley and Ives, 2008; Waldron 2009). However, if researchers inadvertently conflate criteria, findings cannot be truly comparable.

Apparently high frequencies of a spine anomaly termed ‘sacralization’ were observed in human remains associated with two well-known warships: the sixteenth century English *Mary Rose*, and the seventeenth century Swedish warship *Kronan*. Whereas the 16.7% true prevalence observed in

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both samples was interesting, the actual aim of this paper is to highlight that many researchers, including osteoarchaeologists and clinicians working with living patients, conflate criteria for sacralization. This can give findings from less than 2% to as high as 46% for diagnosing prevalence in both skeletal and living populations.

Transitional vertebrae

The adult human hip girdle is comprised of two pelvic bones and a sacrum: the latter serves as the base for the vertebral column and is composed of five fused vertebrae of increasingly smaller size. The sacrum fuses in adolescence and is non-mobile; the 'true' and 'mobile' vertebral column is formed of 24 separate but articulating vertebrae (Bass 2005: 93). From neck to hips, the different vertebral types are cervical (usually seven); the 12 thoracic vertebrae which articulate with the lumbar vertebrae; and the (usually) five lumbar vertebrae, in which L1 articulates with T12, and L5 articulates with the first sacral vertebra S1. Each type of vertebra is physically larger as one moves down the spine from cervical to lumbar, and each individual vertebra is increasingly larger within each category: this is due to increased weight bearing obligations of each type and each individual vertebra (White and Folkens 2000; Bass 2005).

A project was devised to investigate the spinal anomaly termed lumbosacral transitional vertebrae with a focus on sacralization, in order to categorize, if possible, the apparently high occurrence of this anomaly observed in remains from the *Mary Rose*. Criteria used to rate sacra for this trait were therefore compared across studies and an unexpected problem came to light.

The studied skeletal elements are from the early modern warships *Mary Rose* and *Kronan*. The term 'lumbosacral transitional vertebrae' (LSTV) refers to assimilation of the lowest lumbar vertebra (usually L5) to the sacrum, referred to as a sacralized lumbar vertebra; or a first sacral vertebra that has failed to fuse to the other sacral elements and thus remains mobile, termed a lumbarized sacrum. Such vertebrae are described as 'transitioned' to the adjacent vertebral type (Abitbol 1987, Elster 1989, Barnes 1994: 79; Aufderheide and Rodriguez-Martin 1998: 65-66; Roberts and Cox 2003; Bron *et al.* 2007; Barnes 2008). Due to the rarity of lumbarization, only variants of sacralization will be discussed below, but sacra observed to have four segments will be noted.

Figure 1 illustrates both sacralization and a normal sacrum. **Figures 1a** and **1b** show a sacrum with six segments: complete (bony) bilateral fusion of the fifth lumbar vertebra and sacrum, or a sacralized fifth lumbar vertebra; **Figures 1c** and **1d** demonstrate a normal sacrum.

Figure 1. Sacralized and Normal sacra. 1a, 1b: *Mary Rose* Skeleton 43 with bilateral complete sacralization of the fifth lumbar vertebra. 1a is anterior, 1b posterior. **1c, 1d:** *Mary Rose* Skeleton 1, normal sacrum. 1c anterior, 1d posterior.

The anomaly is presumed developmental in origin, a combination of environment and genetics (Barnes 1994; Tague 2009). Early in embryonic development, the anomaly can be triggered by a delay in formation of a vertebral unit (Barnes 1994: 80). If this occurs at the border of two types of vertebra, this can lead to a ‘border shift’: in the lumbosacral region, a cranial (upward) shift results in sacralization of the L5. A caudal border shift results in lumbarization of S1. However, one researcher has suggested some fusion patterns may be due to trauma or pathology (Lanier 1954); and another researcher investigates possible load-bearing benefit related to the size and position of the auricular surface, and sacralization (Mahato 2010a). Barnes (1994: 110) cites researchers who claim that assimilation of the lowest lumbar vertebra into the sacrum can add strength as well as height to the sacrum; and describes sacralization, or cranial border shifting as more common in females than males (ibid: 80).

Sacralization

Sacralization has eight variations. One type, considered the earliest stage, is hypertrophy of one or both transverse (side) processes of the fifth lumbar vertebra (Abitbol 1987). In another type, L5 transverse processes are enlarged enough to come into contact with adjacent first sacral vertebra transverse processes and contact facets form on inferior aspects of vertebral transverse processes and superior sacral processes (alae); this is considered partial, unfused sacralization and can be unilateral or bilateral. Full bony ankylosis between vertebral process and ala, either unilateral or bilateral, is considered complete sacralization. Mixed normal, partial and complete types on left or right sides can occur (Tini *et al.* 1977; Magora and Schwartz 1978, Castellvi *et al.* 1984; Barnes 1994; Luoma *et al.* 2004; Waldron 2009). Contact facets, also termed cranial and caudal platforms, range from smooth-surfaced plaques to highly irregular surfaces.

When considering all variants of both partial and complete unions, sacralization occurs in approximately 2%-10% of prehistoric or medieval populations as reported in general texts (Barnes 1994: 111; Aufderheide and Rodriguez-Martin 1998: 66, Roberts and Cox 2003) and from 1.5%-8% in more specific studies (Masnicová and Beňuš 2003, Sarry and El Banna 2006) (**Table 1**). However, partial versus complete sacralizations are rarely differentiated in archaeological reports. For example, sacralization was reported in 6.9% individuals from a medieval Slovakian cemetery in Masnicová and Beňuš (2003), but incidence was not delineated by variant; a 1972 study of 33 proto-historic Californians cited in Barnes (1994: 111) claims a prevalence of over 27%, but neither the type nor degree is specified: the anomaly is merely described as “transitional lumbosacral vertebrae” (ibid). Barnes (1994) states that bilateral bony ankylosis is the “least common” variant and is “asymptomatic” (ibid: 108), whereas unilateral complete union will lead to rotation of the lumbar spine, resulting in scoliosis; and can cause low back pain and sciatica (ibid: 110).

Table 1. Summary of clinical and archaeological studies of transitional vertebrae, listing authors, number of participants/specimens and technique, and type of lesion (if specified): Partial union (L5 transverse processes expanded; contact platforms; fibrous ankyloses) and Complete union (bony continuity between L5 transverse process and sacral ala, on one or both sides) specified if known.

Study	Number of specimens, technique; population,	Lumbosacral transitional vertebrae (LSTV) observed including type	Frequency
CLINICAL STUDIES			
Moore 1925	87 anatomical specimens, gross observation; USA, ancestry not specified	3 LSTV, bony union	3.4% bony union
Tini et al 1977	4000 radiographs, Switzerland	269 sacra with unilateral or bilateral bony fusion	6.7% bony union
Magora and Schwartz 1978	312 low back pain patients, 148 controls, radiographs; Scandinavia.	20.8% LSTV	13.9% 'complete'
Elster 1989	2000 radiographs, with CT and MRI; USA, ancestry not specified.	140 LSTV bony fusion.	7% bony union
Eyo et al. 2001	300 radiographs; Nigeria	112 Complete and incomplete combined.	37%: not separated into partial and complete fusions
Luoma et al. 2004	138 low back pain patients, 25 controls, MRI; Finland	30% LSTV, both partial and complete fusions combined	30% including partial and complete.
Tague RG. 2009	2086 sacra, anatomical specimens, gross observation; USA Blacks and Whites	131 sacra with completely fused sacralized lumbar vertebrae	6.3% bony union
Mahato 2010b	330 anatomical specimens, gross observation; India.	20 with bilateral or unilateral bony fusion	6.1% bony fusion
Apazidis et al 2011	211 radiographs; USA, general population	75 sacra (35.6%) LSTV, all types combined; 9 with unilateral or bilateral bony fusion	4.3% bony fusion
Dharati et al 2012	189 sacra, anatomical specimens, gross observation; Gujarat India.	21 with unilateral or bilateral bony fusion	11.1% bony fusion
ARCHAEOLOGICAL STUDIES			

Bennett 1972 (cited in Barnes 1994: 111)	33 individuals from northern California. Modoc Native Americans, proto-historic site	9 of 33 with 'transitional lumbosacral vertebrae', type and degree not specified.	27.3% type not specified.
Coyne 1981 (cited in Barnes 1994:111)	108 skeletons, 84 adults, 24 nonadults. Southwestern Anasazi, Native American, prehistoric.	3 sacra (2.8%) with unilateral incomplete lumbarization, one sacrum (1/108 or 0.9%) with unilateral incomplete sacralization.	0.9% unilateral incomplete sacralisation.
Masnicová and Beňuš 2003	DH: 217 burials, 112 sacra; FR:112 burials, 29 sacra, gross observation; SW Slovakia, medieval	DH: 9/112 FR: 2/29 LSTV described as unilateral or bilateral, partial or complete, not broken down by type.	DH: 8.0% type not specified. FR: 6.9% type not specified.
Sarry El-Din and El Banna 2006	270 skeletons, gross observation; Old Kingdom Egypt.	6 LSTV, with 4 sacralized. Partial and complete fusions counted.	1.5% type not specified.

LSTV = lumbosacral transitional vertebrae; DH: Devín-Hrad; FR: Devín-Za kostolom; SW: Southwest

All eight sacralization types are classified in clinical medicine (Tini *et al.* 1977, Castellvi *et al.* 1984; Apazidis *et al.* 2011) but are not always clearly applied (Table 1). For example, Magora and Schwartz (1978) report 20.8% sacralization in a study of 312 back pain patients and 148 controls, but then qualify this as “one third were partial and two-thirds complete” for a rate of 14% bony ankyloses (ibid: 135). Reported clinical rates thus vary widely, from as low as 3.4 % (Moore 1925) to as high as 46% (males in Eyo *et al.* 2001). Some clinical studies fail to state if they refer to sacralization or lumbarization, or openly conflate stages. Transitional vertebrae merit clinical attention due to potential surgical errors related to miscounting vertebrae (Bron *et al.* 2007) and in investigations of low back pain and disc degeneration (Tini *et al.* 1977, Magora and Schwartz 1978, Elster 1989, Eyo *et al.* 2001, Luoma *et al.* 2004, Aihara *et al.* 2005, Bron *et al.* 2007).

In clinical studies, the total sample of individuals (patients and controls; anatomical specimens) can be assessed for LSTV, with true prevalence a ratio of total possible cases. However, with archaeological remains, recovery of sacra is a matter of taphonomy, and one cannot presume absence or presence of this anomaly on unexamined elements. In the Brothwell *et al.* (2000) study of 542 early medieval individuals cited in Roberts and Cox (2003: 180), only 183 sacra were available for observation, with 10 cases of transitional vertebrae providing a crude rate of 5.5%. These few cases cannot be further extrapolated to the entire assemblage. The *Mary Rose* and *Kronan* samples are similarly restricted to crude prevalence rates of available sacra and not to ‘individuals’, since very few can be confidently reassembled (During 1997, Stirland 2005b).

Without a full vertebral column, most researchers claim one cannot be certain where a border transition has occurred, but skeletal elements within the *Kronan* and *Mary Rose* collections are commingled. This study utilizes only recovered sacra and any articulating or clearly associated L5 vertebrae (see Materials); assessment methodology is based on Tague’s (2009) study of 2086 documented remains from the Hamann-Todd and Terry collections, in which he examines “high assimilation sacra” (Tague 2009: 429). Tague primarily investigates the effect of an enlarged sacrum on pelvic inlet size and potential obstetrical complications (ibid: 430), and accordingly his criteria for identifying high assimilation sacra include morphological changes (see Methods) applied to the samples here (ibid: 431).

Mary Rose and Kronan specimens

During analyses of skeletal remains from the *Mary Rose* between 2008 and 2011, apparently high frequency of LSTV, primarily sacralization was observed. When general paleopathology texts and clinical studies were consulted (i.e., Tini *et al.* 1977; Magora and Schwartz 1978; Barnes 1994; Aufderheide and Rodriguez-Martin 1998; Tague 2009), reported rates of 2-14% seemed much lower than that observed in the Tudor remains. Archaeological studies also reported rates of 1.5% to 8% (Masnicová and Beňuš 2003, Sarry and El Banna 2006). The discrepancy between literature and observation became interesting.

The opportunity to examine remains from the *Kronan* arose, providing another sample of individuals known to have died during a war-time shipwreck, and thus a second sample of active, ambulatory individuals who were ‘at work’ at the time of known cause of death. Being the result of mass disasters, the assemblages also offer a chance to analyze individuals, within each sample, who lived contemporaneously. Thus the aim of the project was to investigate rates of sacralization between broadly similar groups, and to see if both groups had similarly ‘high’ rates of the anomaly. Comparable rates would suggest some common aspect between the samples. Alternatively, similarly high rates would indicate LSTV are underreported in medieval and early modern western European populations.

For this project, sacra from the *Mary Rose* are compared with sacra from the *Kronan*, and examples of partial and complete, asymmetrical and symmetrical sacralization are described. Cases of lumbarization are also identified. In addition, criteria for rating individuals (or isolated sacra) as having complete sacralization are compared across a range of studies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

This project focuses on sacra from the English warship *Mary Rose*, capsized and wrecked in 1545 (Rule 1980; Stirland 2005a) and the Swedish warship *Kronan* (‘Crown’), lost due to explosion in 1676 (Franzen 1981, 18; During 1997; Einarsson 1997). Other elements from the pelvic girdle such as fifth lumbar vertebrae and os coxae were also examined, but only if clearly articulating with a sacrum. For each ship, the skeletal remains are commingled, and thus each assemblage represents senior officers, soldiers and mariners (Stirland 2000a: 54; During 1997: 592).

Mary Rose

It is estimated 500 or more men were aboard the *Mary Rose* when it sank 19 July 1545 during a confrontation with the French, with around 35 surviving; elements from approximately 200 men were recovered (Stirland 2005b). A contemporary document, the Anthony Roll, specified 200 seamen, 185 soldiers and 30 gunners were on board, as well as an unknown number of commanding officers comprised of gentry (Stirland 2000a: 54). Work on stable isotopes from 18 individuals suggests a variety of European countries, including Spain, are represented in the *Mary Rose* sample (Bell *et al.* 2009); but this has been disputed by researchers claiming only one of the 18 were born outside the British Isles (Millard and Schroeder 2009).

Remains were catalogued and if possible grouped into 92 Fairly Complete Skeletons (FCS) by Ann Stirland during the early 1980s (Stirland 2005a: 76), which are catalogued by the *Mary Rose* Trust (MRT) as MR 1, MR 2, MR 3 on up to MR 92. Between 2008-2011, most FCS were examined in numerical order (MR 1, MR 2, MR 3 etc.) at the request of the Trust. In a FCS, if a

sacrum and one or both pelvises were present, the bones were tested for sacroiliac articulation to establish confidence the elements were from one individual; if present, fifth lumbar vertebrae were similarly tested. Observations were compared with measurements and notes recorded by Stirland in the early 1980s (available at MRT). Stirland did not always document sacralization, but her findings match this study whenever she did; she focused more on pre-sacral vertebrae, os acromiale, and asymmetry in the shoulder girdle (Stirland 1992; Stirland and Waldron 1997).

Kronan

It is reported that 850 men were on board the *Kronan* when the ship exploded and sank on 1 June 1676 (Franzen 1981, 18; During 1997; Einarsson 1997), including 500 seaman and 350 soldiers (During 1997: 330); 42 men reportedly survived. The *Kronan* remains are not sorted into individuals, but grouped by element. In addition to sacra, all available fifth (or apparently fifth) lumbar vertebrae were examined for caudal platforms, but in the end, only L5 vertebrae directly associated with sacra (by string) were assessed.

Skeletal elements are organised in a numbered *låda* (box), and stored in a *påse* (bag). Similar elements are grouped in closely numbered *påsar*. By looking carefully through all the *lådor*, sacral fragments and complete sacra were identified. Two vertebral columns complete with sacra were connected by string.

Methods

Sacralizations are rated *Complete*, with full bony fusion of an L5 transverse process to the adjacent sacral ala; or *Partial*, with the development of contact facets or raised plaques of articulating platforms on superior alae and/or inferior L5 transverse processes, and lacking bony fusion on either side (Tini *et al.* 1977; Castellvi *et al.* 1984; Abitbol 1987). Complete and partial types are further elaborated upon below. Most studies recognize expanded L5 transverse processes as the earliest stage of transition (Tini *et al.* 1977; Abitbol 1987). All types can be unilateral or bilateral, with different types in combination (e.g. complete fusion on left, contact facets on right; one side normal, other complete or partial).

All 92 individuals identified as FCS by Stirland (2005a) were examined by one author between February 2008 and November 2011 at the Mary Rose Trust, in numerical order (eg. MR Skeleton 1, MR Skeleton 2, MR Skeleton 3 etc) with 86 examined adequately for this project: visits were curtailed as staff prepared for a new museum. Notes and detailed photographs were examined by the other author. The *Kronan* sacra were examined by the first author in June 2011; the second author is familiar with the collection and has also examined these images.

It is acknowledged that some photographs are imperfect: the hand of one author can be seen in several photographs. But this reflects field conditions: the difficulty and expense related to research. Digital photographs were not routinely taken during the earliest visits to the Mary Rose Trust, and due to limited access to the remains, flawed images cannot be rectified in the near future. In Stockholm, sacra were photographed quickly, as the visit could only last three days. The *Kronan* remains are commingled, often boxed by type of bone, and are not individually marked with catalogue numbers. Due to the speed with which they were examined over a short period, some photographs are also regrettably imperfect and cannot be readily reshot.

It has not been practical to return to either location and take additional images: which are not the focus of study; and sacra are curved. They must be propped or held. It was determined cropped images would limit observations of readers. [Alternatives: Hands have been cropped from

photographs, but the complete image is available upon request; or line drawings can be substituted.]

Complete sacralization

Bilateral completely sacralized lumbar vertebrae are counted when both transverse processes are fused to both alae (**Figures 1a, 1b, Figure 2**). In unilateral complete fusion, one transverse process of the L5 is fused to the adjacent sacral ala, while the other transverse process may be enlarged and extended; developing contact platforms; or appear perfectly normal. The L5 vertebra may be retroflexed, and the new alae fused asymmetrically (**Figures 2a and 2b**) (Tague 2009). Bony fusion on one side was considered adequate for designation of Complete (after Tini *et al.* 1977).

Figure 2. Sacralized lumbar vertebrae with bilateral ankylosis. *Kronan* 31.2 with retroflexed L5, asymmetrical fusion, and hiatus between former L5 and S1. **2a** anterior view, **2b** posterior view, proximal aspect. **2c, 2d:** *Kronan* 8.5, symmetrical bilateral complete sacralization. **2c** is anterior view, **2d** posterior. Note: sacra are curved and cannot rest easily on a surface for images.

In relatively complete sacra without an obviously abnormally fused L5, fully sacralized lumbar vertebrae were counted when a sacrum has more than the typical five segments, and thus five pairs of sacral foramina, since a sacralized lumbar vertebra retains foramina for the fifth lumbar nerves (Moore 1925: 272). Cases of fusion of the coccyx were excluded.

Typically, the lumbar transverse processes and sacral alae, and facets from both the lumbar and first sacral vertebrae will fuse (Barnes 1994). The fused lumbar transverse processes will generally be oriented posteriorly toward the auricular surface (Mahato 2010a, b), which may be larger than typical, and the new alae have notably inferior positioning (Mahato 2010b). This morphology is referred to as “dropped” in **Results** and is shown in **Figures 1a, 2a, and 2c**. The former S1 may

retain its promontory and an unusually wide hiatus may persist between L5 and S1 (Barnes 1994; Tague 2009; Mahato 2010b). In assessing remains from the *Mary Rose*, a persistent hiatus was problematic due the overall young age at death for most crew members. In life, this junction typically fuses at around age 30 (Scheuer and Black 2004) and thus many normal sacra retain a hiatus between S1 and S2. In other cases, subsequent to sacralization, the vertebral bodies (centrae) of L5 and S1 can fuse together (Lanier 1954; Tague 2009; Mahato 2010a, 2010b).

Two other observations were used to support rating isolated archaeological specimens as displaying Complete Sacralization: unaligned, incomplete fusion of the inferior facets of former L5 with the dorsal sacral surface; and, with the former S3 now an S4 in a high assimilation sacrum (Tague 2009), the typical ventral curve normally present on an S3 will begin or be predominately located within the new S4. For comparison, a normal sacrum is shown in **Figure 1c and 1d**.

Partial sacralization

Highly remodelled, spiculated articulations between L5 transverse processes and sacral alae, with contact platforms fitting tightly, are considered fused in most clinical studies, due to development of a fibrous union (Aihara *et al.* 2005: 688) (**Figure 3**). However, fibrous union was not counted as Complete, following Barnes (1994) and Tague (2009), but rated as Partial. In other types of partial sacralization, articulating platforms can be observed on the superior aspects of sacral alae and inferior aspects of lumbar transverse processes. The developing platforms may be flattened facets, elevated plaques or articulating new joints that fall short of interlocking spiculations found in fibrous unions.

Figure 3. Fibrous ankylosis. *Mary Rose* Skeleton 75 **3a**: Anterior view. **3b**: Superior aspect, ventral is at top of image. Note spiculated surface on left ala articulation and smoother concavity on right.

Fifth lumbar vertebrae with notably extended and enlarged transverse processes were counted as Partial which is considered a type of partial LSTV (Tini *et al.* 1977) or early stage of sacralization (Abitbol 1987). Sacra with reduced segments potentially due to a lumbarized S1 were identified. Sacra with proximal indicators of sacralization, such as ‘dropped’ alae but extensive distal post-mortem bone loss, and those with apparently six segments but only four pairs of sacral foramina and thus likely due to coccygeal fusion were not counted as sacralized, but counted as “unsure” or Six Segment Sacra (**Tables 4-5**).

Estimations of age at death cohorts are based on common pelvic and sacral indicators, including fusion of sacral elements (Scheuer and Black 2004: 217), hiatus between S1/S2, development of annular rings, and morphological appearance of the auricular surface. When sacra articulate with associated pelvic bones, additional indicators from these bones were used such as age-related changes to (pelvic) auricular surfaces and pubic symphyses; and epiphyseal fusion of iliac crests, ischial tuberosities and anterior-inferior spines (Krogman 1962; Buikstra and Ubelaker 1994). Sacra from individuals are labelled with FCS numbers for *Mary Rose* and by bag number for

Kronan, and are assigned to age at death cohorts. Remains are described as *juvenile* if sacral elements were unfused; *adolescent/young adult* if sacral elements were fused but retained hiatus (age 15-20); *young adult* (20-30) if there is a hiatus between the first and second sacral vertebrae, with the annular ring in development or present and youthful; and *adult* if S1 and S2 were fused, annular rings complete, and sacral auricular surfaces no longer striated and ‘billowy’.

For both assemblages, sacra and clearly associated L5 vertebrae were examined for unilateral and bilateral fusion and articulating platforms, age at death, with type of LSTV ascertained as described. Both unilateral and bilateral full bony fusions are grouped together as Complete in **Results (Tables 4 and 5)**. Statistical testing was carried out, with significance tested using likelihood-ratio X^2 tests (G-tests), unless the expected outcome was lower than 5 in any cell, in which case Fisher’s Exact Test was used. The P value <0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

The sacra and fifth lumbar vertebrae from each ship are described below, in **Tables 2 and 3**. Each table also states if evidence for transitional vertebrae are observed. Both warship samples retain 60 assessable sacra and within each sample, 10 (16.7%) have unilateral or bilateral bony ankylosis. **Tables 4 and 5** examine the transitional vertebrae or affected sacra as observed within each sample, including all observed types of LSTV, including partial and complete.

Mary Rose

All examined FCS are listed in Results Table 2, regardless of applicability for this study. MR 32 is omitted as the box contains multiple tibiae from at least three individuals, and six FCS from late in the series were not adequately examined before visits to the MRT became impossible as staff prepared for the new museum. Most sacra are complete and in excellent condition: the anaerobic environment that developed within months of the shipwreck resulted in exceptional preservation (Stirland 2005a). Age estimations for the 92 ‘individuals’ range from pre-adolescent to adult (Stirland 2005a). Two individuals, MR 55 and MR 71 are estimated to be aged 12-14 years and were probably cabin boys (ibid). MR 55 retains a sacrum with all elements unfused and was assessed for sacralization. The sample thus includes individuals from pre-adolescence to mature adult, with an average estimated age at death of 26.8 years (**Table 2**).

[Table 2 near here]

Kronan

The remains are often boxed by type. Every box was opened and examined, but not all boxes are listed. Accordingly, boxes that lack sacra or for example only contain femora or several crania are omitted; all assessable sacra are listed in **Table 3**, identified by påse (bag). Ten fragmented sacra, generally a section of a dorsal aspect, were omitted. This table also provides estimated age cohorts from juvenile to adult. In a few cases, part or all of the vertebral column was stored with the sacrum and indeed attached by string; in several instances one or both os coxae were stored with the sacrum and articulated unambiguously. In these cases, additional information from vertebrae and os coxae could aid in age cohort justification.

[Table 3 near here]

Mary Rose lumbosacral transitional vertebrae

Within the 86 ‘individuals’ from the *Mary Rose*, 60 retain assessable lumbosacral regions. Estimations of age at death are fairly evenly split, with 31 sacra from juveniles /adolescents/ young adults, and 29 from those estimated to be aged 30 and above. Considering the entire sample of 60 sacra, thirty-one sacra are normal (51.7%) (**Table 2**); if all types of LSTV are combined, including complete and partial sacralization and lumbarization, 23 of 60 sacra (38.3%) have some variant of transitioned vertebrae.

Ten have bilateral (n= 9) or unilateral (n= 1, MR 35) sacralization of L5 (16.7%) with bony ankylosis (i.e. complete sacralization), two sacra have four vertebral elements and are thus lumbarized (3.3%) (**Tables 4 and 7**). Ten additional sacra and associated L5s have articulating cranial/caudal facets or ‘platforms’ (16.7%), including one (MR 63) with bilateral fibrous ankylosis; an eleventh has an L5 with notably expanded transverse processes. These last 11 are considered partial sacralizations.

Table 4 Results: *Mary Rose* crew with sacralization type of lumbosacral transitional vertebrae, specified as Complete (unilateral or bilateral bony fusion) or Partial with development of articulating platforms. Includes one possible Partial, atypical sacra, and those rated ‘Unsure’. Most sacra were relatively complete. States if articulation os coxae are present. Includes age estimation.

Skeleton	Sacralization	Articulating Os Coxae?	Age Cohort
Complete LSTV: Bony ankylosis (afterTague 2009:431)			
MR 02	Yes	No	yA
MR 06	Yes	Yes	A
MR 12	Yes	Yes	A
MR 13	Yes	Yes	A
MR 16	Yes	Yes	A
MR 26	Yes	Yes	yA
MR 35	Yes unilateral L	Yes	A
MR 43	Yes	Yes	A
MR 78	Yes	Yes	yA
MR 79	Yes	No	yA
Possible Sacralization			
MR 63	Bilateral fibrous ankylosis (possibly complete and broken post-mortem)	Yes	A
Partial: Cranial platforms on S1, Caudal platforms on L5, L5 processes enlarged			
MR 4	Unilateral S1 L cranial platform	No	yA
MR 10	Bilateral S1 cranial L5 caudal platforms	Yes	A
MR 11	Bilateral S1 cranial L5 caudal platforms	Yes	A
MR 18	Bilateral S1 cranial L5 caudal platforms	Yes	A
MR 41	Bilateral S1 cranial platforms	Yes	yA
MR 44	Unilateral S1 R cranial platform	L only	A
MR 50	Unilateral S1 R cranial platform	Yes	A
MR 52	Unilateral S1 R cranial platform	R only	yA
MR 75	Fibrous ankylosis L, S1 cranial L5 caudal platform R	Yes	yA
MR 91	L5 transverse process extended	R only	yA
Sacra with 4 or 6 segments			
MR 19	6 segment sacrum with coccyx fused	No	A

MR 58	Sacrum 4 segments	Yes	yA
MR 69	S1 lumbarized? Sacrum 4 segments, Six lumbar vertebrae, S1/L6 bilateral caudal platforms	No	A
Unsure if Sacralized			
MR 23	S1 resembles sacralized L5, but sacrum 5 segments	Yes	A
MR 38	6 sacral segments or L5 sacralized	No	A
MR 40	S1 resembles sacralised L5, auricular expanded, but distal eroded	Yes	A
MR 51	S1 resembles sacralised L5, but sacrum 5 segments	Yes	A
MR 85	Possible: S1 resembles sacralised L5 but distal eroded	Yes	A

R = right, L = left, L5 = fifth lumbar, S1 = first sacral segment. yA=young adult, A=adult (see text for age ranges)

Kronan lumbosacral transitional vertebrae

Rates of sacralization are identical between the two ships, but sacra from the *Kronan* were not as well-preserved as those from the *Mary Rose*. Approximately 70 sacra or sacral fragments are available, with 60 complete enough for study (22 sacra determined to be from younger individuals, and 38 sacra from adults): 37 sacra had post-mortem bone loss (61.7%) yet retained adequate material, even if only an S1 to examine for cranial platforms (**Table 3**). Thirty-six sacra (60.0%) had normal lumbosacral regions. Sixteen (26.7%) had evidence of some type of sacralization vertebrae, with all types combined. When differentiated, 10 sacra have complete bilateral bony fusions (16.7%). Six partial sacralizations (10.0%) were observed, specifically four with articulation platforms (6.7%), and two L5 vertebrae (11c, 56a) with expanding transverse processes (3.3%) (**Tables 5 and 8**).

Three sacra (*påsar* 2.10; 13.7a; 52) were clearly comprised of 6 segments, apparently due to fused coccyx. One sacrum (78) has inferiorly positioned, asymmetrically fused alae, but the distal is too eroded to presume sacralization; and the fourth sacral vertebra (or S3 if L5 was sacralized) is reduced to a thin vertical plate of bone as the result of an apparent crush injury. Five sacra (8.3%) were too fragmentary or ambiguous to permit categorizing. None of the *Kronan* sacra show evidence of lumbarization.

Table 5 Results. *Kronan* sacra and fifth lumbar vertebrae suggesting sacralization, specified as Complete (unilateral or bilateral bony fusion) or Partial with development of articulating platforms, or lumbar transverse processes expanded. Includes those rated 'Unsure'. Condition of sacra included. Includes age cohort estimates. Sacra occasionally associated using string with L5 or even most of vertebral column; less often associated with one or both os coxae. Most sacra somewhat complete, but many with distolateral erosion.

Påse (Bag)	LSTV	Sacrum or L5 complete	Age cohort
Complete Sacralization: Bony ankylosis (after Tague 2009: 431)			
4.8	Alae dropped; L5/S1 hiatus; S1 retains promontory; 5 pr sacral foramina	Complete	A
5.2a	L5 transverse processes (alae) fused asymmetrically; 5 pr foramina	Complete	A
5.2b	Alae dropped; hiatus between L5 and S1; 5 pr foramina	Complete	A
8.5	Alae dropped, promontory S1; 5 pr foramina	Complete	A

13.7b	S1 promontory, alae dropped; 5 pr foramina	Distal eroded	A
31.2	Asymmetrical alae; large L5/S1 hiatus; S1 promontory; 5 pr foramina	Distal eroded	A
37.15	Alae dropped, large L5/S1 hiatus; 5 pr foramina	Complete	A
56d	Alae dropped, 5 pr foramina, 'S4' curve	Complete	A
67b	Alae dropped and asymmetrically fused; L5 retroflexed; 'S4' curves, and broken off inferior to large 'S5'	Distal eroded	yA
78	Alae dropped and asymmetrically fused; large L5/S1 hiatus, S3 crush fracture.	Distal eroded	A
Partial: Cranial platforms on S1, Caudal platforms on L5, L5 processes enlarged			
11c	L5 transverse processes expanded, slight bilateral caudal platforms	Complete with L5 attached with string	A
56a	L5 transverse processes expanded	Complete with L5, most of vertebral column attached	yA
71	Bilateral S1 cranial platforms	Proximal sacrum	A
72.1a	Unilateral S1 R cranial platform	S5 eroded	A
76	Bilateral S1 cranial platforms	Complete	yA
79.1b	Bilateral S1 cranial L5 caudal platforms	Complete sacrum, articulating L5	yA
Sacra with 6 segments			
2.10	6 sacral vertebrae	R lateral eroded	A
13.7a	6 sacral vertebrae	Lateral aspects S2-S6 eroded	A
52	6 sacral vertebrae	Lateral aspects S5-S6 eroded	A
Unsure if Sacralized			
9.3 b	Alae dropped	Eroded at S3	A
38b	Alae notably dropped	S1 plus dorsal plane	A
38c	Possible unilateral S1 cranial platform	S1, S2-S4 centrae	A
81	Alae dropped; morphology 'S2', 'S4' suggest LSTV	Distal eroded	yA
85	6 sacral vertebrae, S4 curved	Slight erosion R distal	A

R = right, L = left, L5 = fifth lumbar, S1, S3, S4 = sacral vertebrae, pr= pair, yA = young adult, A = adult, ages 30+

Statistics

Statistical analyses of *Mary Rose* and *Kronan* crews, comparing ships, age cohorts, sacralized elements and normal sacra were calculated using values in **Tables 6**.

The age distribution between the ships show a statistically significant difference ($\chi^2_{1df}=6.200$, $p=0.0128$), with the *Kronan* crew being older. When sacralization is compared with normal sacra separated by age for each ship, older adults show more sacralization, though not to a statistically significant degree (*Mary Rose* FET, $p=0.065$, *Kronan* FET, $p=0.064$). However, comparing both samples taken together, the higher frequency of sacralization among older crew members is statistically significant ($\chi^2_{1df}=7.478$, $p<0.01$).

[Table 6 near here]

DISCUSSION

Sacralization: under-reported and misunderstood

Skeletal remains from the wrecks of the 16th century Tudor warship *Mary Rose* and 17th century Swedish warship *Kronan*, both lost in documented disasters, have been examined for evidence consistent with transitional vertebrae. Both lumbarized (four segment) and sacralized (six segment) sacra were identified (**Tables 2 – 5**), but this paper has focused on sacralization, due to the lack of lumbarization from the *Kronan* and thus the low prevalence of lumbarization in this study. Sacralization is far more common (Ortner 2003: 463) and thus more likely to be encountered and recognized in the field; and incomplete sacra cannot be assessed for number of elements.

Simplified tables of the *Mary Rose* and *Kronan* results are found in **Table 7** (*Mary Rose*) and **Table 8** (*Kronan*).

[**Table 7 and Table 8 near here**]

The total frequency of LSTV in the *Mary Rose* sample of 38.3%, with all types counted together, compares well to clinical reports (**Table 1**), in which rates of up to 37% of transitional vertebrae are observed (Eyo *et al.* 2001; Luoma *et al.* 2004) and in which all types (including lumbarization) are also combined. In the *Kronan* assemblage, 16 sacra (26.7%) had evidence of some type of sacralization, with all types combined. However, Eyo *et al.* (2001) and Luoma *et al.* (2004) should not otherwise be compared to the results from this study, as these authors conflate all types.

If fully sacralized elements with bony ankylosis from either ship are compared to clinical and archaeological reports (**Table 1**), the rate of 16.7% is markedly higher than the 1.5% to 8% from most studies, and somewhat higher than 11.1% (Dharati *et al.* 2012) and 14% (Magora and Schwartz 1978) observed in clinical studies. The Magora and Schwartz (1978) investigation is of interest, since the subjects are Scandinavian. If observations in studies can be split into partial and complete types permitting the same types to be compared, it would be easier to compare rates between and within populations.

There are statistically significant differences in the age group distributions between the ships when considering only sacra with complete bony ankylosis of the fifth lumbar, or those with no evidence of the anomaly at all (**Table 6**), a subset consisting of 41 *Mary Rose* sacra and 46 sacra from the *Kronan*. The *Mary Rose* sample is mostly young (27/41), the *Kronan* sample mostly adult (28/46), and comparing ‘young’ versus ‘old’ between ships, regardless of sacra, is statistically significant: the crew of the *Kronan* was older than that on the *Mary Rose*.

More adults than younger individuals are affected on the *Mary Rose*, although not significantly, and also on the *Kronan*, where there is a significant difference in sacralization between age cohorts. When comparing sacralization between age cohorts in total, the younger crew members have significantly less sacralization, and indeed, 59.7% (40/67) of the normal sacra from both ships are rated as young adult.

The distribution of sacralization between the crews is not significant. Young adults, including juveniles, when compared between ships show no significant difference; nor is there any significant differences among adults of both ships; nor when comparing normal sacra and sacralization between the ships regardless of age. This is unsurprising since both samples have equal numbers of sacralization, and similar numbers of normal sacra. The significant differences are between age cohorts on both ships, regardless of sacral traits. The reason for the different distribution in age groups is difficult to explain and could be a coincidence due to small sample size. An alternative explanation could be that the older crew were picked from another geographical region where the predisposition for this anomaly was more common. Because

sacralization and indeed any type of transitional vertebrae are considered to be developmental disorders, with the triggering incident occurring during foetal development (Barnes 1994; Tague 2009), the age at death should not influence the incidence of sacralization, but perhaps has provided time for the trait to be fully expressed.

Physiology and morphology

Transitional vertebrae display altered spinal functions and resemble adjacent vertebral types. With sacralization there is a loss of mobility for a fifth lumbar vertebra after fusion with the sacrum; with lumbarization, the first sacral segment gains mobility (Abitbol 1987; Barnes 1994; Mahato 2010a, 2010b; Dharati *et al.* 2012). Physiological differences related to a six-segment sacrum include increased articulation of sacrum and ilium, resulting in increased trunk support in locomotion (Abitbol 1987). Mahato (2010a, 2010b) has studied 330 sacra in India and notes that the expanded auricular surfaces on sacralized elements, which also often sit lower in the ilia, transmit loads lower into the hips and surmises this provides a benefit (Mahato 2010a: 5). Barnes (1994) cites two researchers who suggest that assimilation of the L5 with the sacrum increases the height and strength of the sacrum, but that such benefits may come with a price: the more common unilateral union can trigger scoliosis as a consequence of unilateral rotation of the lumbar spine, leading to low back pain and sciatica (ibid: 110); the bilateral ankylosis is asymptomatic, but is the “least common” type (ibid: 108).

Clinical studies utilize radiographs, CT and MRI images, and anatomical preparations to investigate prevalence of the anomaly and morphological traits associated with six-segment sacra (**Table 1**) (Tini *et al.* 1977; Tague 2009; Dharati *et al.* 2012). In typical sacra, alae are horizontal and articulate with the ilia as part of the sacroiliac joint (Mahato 2010b). When L5 has fused to S1, the L5 centra and former transverse processes may join S1 symmetrically or asymmetrically; or a gap between L5 and S1 may be retained, with S1 preserving its original promontory (Tague 2009). A typical sacrum begins to curve at S3 distinctly, or curve gently from S3 to S4, with S2 relatively vertical. In sacra presumed to include a sacralized L5, the sacral curve begins or is sharpest at S4, which formerly was S3.

Clinical investigations of LSTV focus on low back pain

Clinical investigations into causes of low back pain (LBP) suggest some correspondence between LBP, disc herniation, severe localized degenerative disc disease, and sacralized fifth lumbar vertebrae (Tini *et al.* 1977; Magora and Schwartz 1978; Elster 1989; Barnes 1994; Eyo *et al.* 2001; Luoma *et al.* 2004; Aihara *et al.* 2005; Bron *et al.* 2007; Apazidis *et al.* 2011). However, direct correlation between sacralization and LBP continues to be debated (Luoma *et al.* 2004; Bron *et al.* 2007). Magora and Schwartz (1978) find that, while sacralization does not seem to predispose one to LBP, pre-existing pain associated with sacralization may be more severe, and they specifically link LBP and occupations that require bending and “sudden maximum effort” (Magora and Schwartz 1978: 143).

Obviously, low back pain cannot be measured among skeletal remains. The presence of various types of sacralization among both crews may indicate the harsh realities of life aboard a warship: despite back pain, one gets on with tasks at hand. Presumed activities can be assumed with a high degree of confidence from the crews of the 16th century *Mary Rose* (Stirland and Waldron 1997: 330) and the 17th century *Kronan* (During 1997: 592). Constant bending and “sudden maximum effort” (Magora and Schwartz 1978, 143) would have been commonplace, with activities including handling guns, cannon and shot; longbow use (on the *Mary Rose*); and hauling sail, ropes and

anchors (Stirland 2000a). Most regular seamen would have worked on ships seasonally, returning home to work on farms, or as day labourers (ibid, 28-31). Any LBP aggravated by sacralization did not stop one from working in a strenuous occupation.

The need to consistently differentiate sacralization types

One study of 300 LBP sufferers in Nigeria found that 46% of male patients had LSTV (Eyo *et al.* 2001: 3) with overall prevalence of both sexes 37% (ibid: 4). The results were separated by sex but not by age or fusion type (ibid). Similarly, a study of 211 abdominal films of adults in the USA who had never undergone lumbosacral surgery (Apazidis *et al.* 2011) found that while 35.6% were classified as having sacralization, most (23.2%) merely showed expanded fifth lumbar transverse processes; 8.1% had cranial and caudal platforms, termed “an articulation” (Apazidis *et al.* 2011: 859). Only 4.2% of the sample (9 of 211) had unilateral or bilateral bony ankyloses, termed “fusion” (ibid). Seven of the nine sacralizations were observed in female patients (Apazidis *et al.* 2011: 861).

Tague (2009) examined 2086 individuals from the Hamann-Todd and Terry Collections for evidence of sacralization, termed “high assimilation sacra” (Tague 2009: 429), in a sample split fairly evenly between sexes and ancestry (Tague 2009: 430). Sacral morphology and articulation with os coxae were evaluated for evidence of sacralization separately from the rest of the spinal column (ibid). Tague found a frequency of 6.3% (131/2086) with no significant differences associated with sex, ancestry or age at death. Only bony ankyloses were counted as high assimilation; neither “distinctive enlargement of the transverse process” of the lowest lumbar vertebra, nor nearthrosis (fibrous ankyloses or platforms) were considered (Tague 2009: 434).

Sacralization rates observed from randomly available remains of two warship crews give identical rates of 16.7% for the same number of sacra from each ship. When compared to 6.3% observed by Tague (2009), 4.2% observed by Apazidis *et al.* (2011) and 1.5%-8% found by Masnicová and Beňuš (2003) and Sarry and El Banna (2006), there seems to be a striking difference between the findings reported here, and in most other studies rating bony fusion separately from other types. The Magora and Schwartz (1978: 135) study of 460 Scandinavians with 14% ‘complete sacralization’ suggests that something related to sample population may be in effect.

CONCLUSIONS

The frequency of sacralization with true bony fusion, as noted in the crews of the *Mary Rose* and the *Kronan* are at odds with the reported prevalence of 2-14% (average 6-7%) for the anomaly, both in modern populations and archaeological remains (**Table 1**). Apparent differences between expected rates and what is observed in two sample populations of mariners suggest that sacralization has been under-recognized in archaeological collections, probably due to the fragility of the sacrum. There was differential preservation between the two assemblages: only eight of the *Mary Rose* sacra had significant post-mortem bone loss, compared to 37 *Kronan* sacra with distal and lateral erosion. Four of the five *Kronan* sacra rated as ‘Unsure’ lacked distal aspects, whereas only two of the five *Mary Rose* sacra were rated ‘Unsure’ due to taphonomy.

Some clinical studies investigating degenerative spinal conditions indicate transitional vertebrae are far more common than this, reporting rates of 20%-46% (Magora and Schwartz 1978; Eyo *et al.* 2001; Apazidis *et al.* 2011), but when types of sacralization are delineated, bony ankyloses drop to as low as 4.2% (Apazidis *et al.* 2011: 859). Some studies attribute the wide range of rates to diagnostic criteria, that is, conflating all eight types as equally representing sacralization (Bron

et al. 2007: 690; Tague 2009: 434). One recommendation is for researchers to consistently document the type of sacralization observed. This excellent advice has been previously advocated (e.g. Bron *et al.* 2007: 690), but is still not widely applied. By specifying the types observed, future studies would be more comparable.

Finally, the samples analysed for this project are much smaller than the 2086 individuals rated by Tague (2009), the hundreds of participants in various clinical studies, or the large collections of archaeological skeletons observed by others (Masnicová and Beňuš 2003, Sarry and El Banna 2006). Using specific criteria to identify complete and partial fusions, other archaeological collections can be assessed with results more easily compared to this study, and to others.

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